

Including people in design processes, good but how?

Engaging with Inclusive Design Methodology through a digital platform

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Abstract: www.designingwithpeople.org is a new web tool created to support and inspire designers to design more inclusively. Constructing this web tool revealed a number of insights, and some thoughts for the future of inclusive design are embedded in it. This paper describes these insights as the rationale of the web tool. From influencing policy and business practices to repositioning the subject of design, the concept of Inclusive Design is evolving. What are the next steps? What are the specific questions for inclusive design practice? We explore *three* more layers of the question, each of which is the title of a subsection:

1. How do we start people-centred design process?
2. What are the methods in user researches for design?
3. What are the ethical procedures when designers design with people?

The answers to these questions are our attempt to offer multiple perspectives in understanding people and the prompt adoption of Web 2.0 technologies. We hope that designers' use of multiple perspectives in understanding people will foster the 'icon' of Inclusive Design methodology, which in turn will facilitate the formation of empathic relationships that lead to emotional connections among participants in the Design Community of Practice.

Key words: *Inclusive Design, Webtool, User Participation and Methodology*

1. Introduction

Since its emergence in the UK in the 1990s, Inclusive Design has been promoted as an important element of business strategy [1] and recently there has been more focus on discussion of the subject in design education [2]. One of the core developments of Inclusive Design in the UK has been the i~design project, a ten-year collaboration between the Engineering Design Centre (EDC) at Cambridge University and the Royal College of Art Helen Hamlyn Centre (RCAHHC), two key players in the field, with other UK collaborators from different sectors. It started in 2000 and has centred on three successive research collaborations, funded by the UK's Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC). Table 1 shows the evolution of this major UK academic collaboration regarding Inclusive Design to date. This has led the way in developing the concept and influencing policy makers by publishing white papers and tools for both business and design communities. Looking ahead, the next questions are: what if majority of policy makers, corporations and members of the design community were all to adopt and practice inclusive design? Which areas would be the next focuses?

Project	Research question	Deliverables
i~design 1: 2000-2004	<i>What is inclusive design?</i>	a knowledge base for inclusive design through the identification, development and testing of models, tools and theories, e.g. BSI definition of inclusive design
i~design 2: 2003-2007	<i>How to enable industry to carry out inclusive design?</i>	develop mechanisms and approaches for inclusive design resulting in a series of business case studies that highlight inclusive design processes and professional models, www.inclusivedesigntoolkit.com
i~design 3: 2006-2010	<i>How to enable designers to design with people more effectively?</i>	(Expecting) Exclusion calculator, www.designingwithpeople.org , etc...

Table 1. The development of i~design projects

2. The digital contributions to people-centred design development

In order to answer these questions, we attempt to reflect on the whole process of managing and organising Inclusive Design activities. As well as successful workshops with designers and students, we want to expand our scope of interaction from face-to-face personal interaction to broader base of participation through websites. The web tool, www.designingwithpeople.org, will provide an educational tool for designers practicing Inclusive Design and other form people-centred designs. As we are inspired by the advocacy of Participatory Design, we hope to build up a Community of Practice (CoPs), defined by Wenger et al. [3], defining CoPs as, ‘groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis.’ This raises the issue of how to foster a sense of communal intimacy within and expanding from this group of people, i.e. from design community to general public.

After the digital world went through the transformation process from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0, the Web world has encouraged more democratic use, and Web 2.0 tools foster interaction, collaboration, and contribution. Users of our web tool are our potential contributors, and their emotional connections, identity recognition, and long lasting commitment, would contribute to the continuity of our webtool, www.designingwithpeople.org, (fig.1) which is the main contribution from the RCAHHC in the final stage of this ten-year collaboration. It collates all the data from our ten years of research and experience and presents it in a comprehensive way and aims to share them in a more accessible way than our organisation website, www.hhc.rca.ac. More important, we aim to provide an education tool to encourage designers to develop their own ways to make connections, not only within their subject area but also beyond it. Compare to the www.inclusivedesigntoolkit.com, main deliverable of the i~design 2 project, which is a very informative web resources of inclusive design, our intention is to work with this website and other resources to develop an interactive platform to enable designer to understand and transfer the principles of Inclusive Design into their own practices.

Three questions for navigating the web tool are presented in the next subsections, along with some reflections from the authors’ experience of practicing and researching Inclusive Design practice and methodology. Over the years, it has been proved that Inclusive Design is a creative process that contributes to inclusivity in society [4]. These subsections present the future implications for Inclusive Design, with a special emphasis on its social impacts as well as on the formation of a *Community of Practice*.

Figure 1. Screen shot of the content page of the www.designingwithpeople.org, first draft, 2009

2.1 How do we start people-centred design process?

The main parts of the web tool are the sections: ACTIVITIES and CHARACTERS (fig.2). They provide two ways for our ‘users’, i.e. designers, to meet their future users virtually before meeting ‘real people’. The ACTIVITIES section is based on the user-centred model, which is driven by insights. The need for information regarding specific people comes later in the process. The first set of insights is from our ten-year track record of inclusive design projects. All their user interaction records from a

wide range of design issues are distilled into ACTIVITIES and include such themes as Personal Care, Household, Work & Money and Communication. The CHARACTERS section is based on a different model, where people’s contributions come first. This is the essence of people-centred design. CHARACTERS contains a series of character profiles that loosely represent the spectrum of abilities and disabilities by five areas: vision, hearing, mobility, dexterity and cognition. They are called the ‘creative partners,’ i.e., individuals with special situations such as disability or being in an older age group. Both the data of capability and the lifestyles of these characters will be mapped. They are different from conventional virtual personas in that they are drawn from the actual design cases that inspired them, and users of the web tool can contact real people afterwards.

Over the decade of Inclusive Design development, different ways to design inclusively have emerged. This ACTIVITIES and CHARACTERS approach represents the two poles of the practice, suitable for different situations. The ACTIVITIES section is more structured and less experimental, where designers still control the flow of the process. Comparatively, CHARACTERS is a people-centred approach that can also lead to people-driven innovation. This distinction is supported by the DTI’s report [5] which adopted the term ‘people’ to replace ‘user’, because ‘...UCD is often thought to be purely about ‘usability’ or making things ‘easy to use’. Frequently, UCD becomes merely ‘user testing’ and is brought in at the end of the product development cycle. In the report, it stated that users are often conceived in a task-centric way that fits into current technology-led business models’. It is clear that user-centred design, which starts from ‘insights’ or social phenomena, is totally different from the practice of people-centred design, which is inspired by ‘people’ without any preconceptions.

The design of this basic part of the web tool is inspired by the practice of virtual ethnography. We endorse Cowlishaw’s [6] reminder about the importance of classical ethnography in the respect of ‘*writing that is based on extended, empirical fieldwork, the “being their”, “going elsewhere”, immersing oneself in some other social space with other social subjects in order to change your mind*’. We too believe that immersing oneself in other ‘stories’ is essential step in the process of understanding people. The key tool is the attempt to experience other people’s worlds *from other* perspectives. We hope that jumping between people-centred design and user-centred design perspective will unglue our fixed mindset and let go the assumption that what happens online gives the real picture of social life and social significance.

Fig.2. ACTIVITIES and CHARACTERS Pages, first draft, 2009

2.2 What are the methods in user researches for design?

In order to make designers and design researchers aware of this distinction between methodologies while they are designing, the METHODS section of the web tool is designed to map out the majority of design methods in practice with new classifications and a catalogue of the types of methodology that these methods belong to. However, unlike social scientists' classifications, we decided to describe the methodology for designers simply as a way of working and a rationale of their interactions with people.

In design, the consideration of the people who are going to benefit from design processes is not a new concept; many humanitarian designers have emphasised this relationship e.g. *Designing for People* (1955) by industrial designer Henry Dreyfuss and *Designing for the Disabled* (1976) by architect Selwyn Goldsmith. However, these relationships between designers and design users have in the past been mainly restricted to a quantitative approach based on measuring people's bodies and analysing the usability of designs in relationship to people's capability. Gradually, this 'designing for' approach has been challenged [7] [8]. This indicates that design practices should consider people's emotions as well as their physical ability to use the design in question. The shift of preposition from 'designing for' to 'designing with' is essential. That is why our web tool is called www.designingwithpeople.org. It offers a 'middle path way' and aims to link both sides, i.e. 'for' and 'by' approaches, and collates all of them into a comprehensive tool to let newcomers pick the appropriate approach. It also works as a benchmark for established practitioners to check where they are in their relationships with people in design.

In the light of this, we design a multiple perspective of user interactions in our web tool. In the METHODS section, we will provide a fixed vintage point on which the reader could find his or her position. In other words, the bonding between the 'readers' and the protagonists depicted in the stories provided in the web tool is 'ambivalent'. We hope that those who consult our website will identify with multiple frames of reference: as designers, as Internet users, as students, and/or as 'onlookers'. We have take advantage of this possible practice of multiple identities to solicit 'readers' to reveal their own values and understanding of social roles in the process of understanding people. Therefore in our web tool, we will present different possible rationale for each kind of activity, such as design for people, with people and by people. Moreover, the readers will be referred to 'study' 'look', 'ask', 'try' and 'dream' (Fig.3). Employing multiple perspectives to understand people should lead to greater changes in the readers' ways of thinking about people. Just as Joinson argued, 'tools are more than just something to make a task easier. They change your way of thinking, of approaching a task (and indeed the nature of the task itself), and can reap unimagined wider social changes' [9].

Method 1: The Methods Lab

A creative workshop to explore new ways to design with people for social change. People with disability are recruited and paid to work as creative partners. They are all briefed to share their everyday lives experience to designers and worked with them to develop new concepts to improve people's lives.

Research Approach

Aim

A more experiential learning experience for participants from different backgrounds. It emphasizes on the interdisciplinary collaboration to address social changes and design exclusion.

Input requirements

Fig.3. METHODS Page
first draft, 2009

Fig.4 METHODS Section

C1: Consent – the essential procedure for all researches (useful guidance: www.doh.gov.uk/consent)

C2: Confidentiality – data and information protection on collaboration

C3: Conduct – wider responsibility for researchers

2.3 What are the ethical procedures when designers design with people?

All new definitions of ‘design’ align with the fundamental philosophy of Inclusive Design, which is to ‘encourage designers to design inclusively and design for social inclusion and for those being excluded by design’ [10].

The more specific question after more than ten years of development might be: how to transform our societies through design? There are many ongoing discourses on this subject and it is not within the realm of this paper to discuss them, but the ETHICS section of the web tool contains information on related organisations and projects for designers to refer to. A common code of ethics is the main part of the section. This section provides three areas for good practice of user research in design. It is based on

Higgins’ three “Cs” model of conducting user research [11]. However, based on our experience in inclusive design, we further developed this model into an ethical procedure for design research. The three Cs become the three levels of questions for design researchers to reflect during the process (fig.4).

3. Conclusions and the Next Step

This article is the outcome of our on-going reflection on the development of our web tool for Inclusive Design, and the evaluation should not only point out the promising areas of this web tool but also present its possible path of future development. Most importantly, it is registered as .org rather than .com, with the aim of suggesting a community or organisation of active design partners in the design research process. However, at the current state, the design of our web tool remains a product in the context of Web 1.0. It is a

traditional way of publishing, relying on our content management systems. It is not yet achieve synchronous and asynchronous, interactive and collaborative system. With our recognition of the importance of the people in facilitating Inclusive Design, our next step is to create an interactive forum on which designers and people could join together to constitute the Community of Practice for Inclusive Design.

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